

VARIATION OF APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME OF NON-ELECTROLYTES IN SOLUTION WITH CONCENTRATION

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The apparent molar volume of a non-electrolyte in solution does not seem to vary very much with variation in concentration in the range of concentration examined.

The variation of apparent molar volume of a solute with concentration has been investigated by a number of workers (Redlich and Rosenfeld, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 186, 65; Scott and Wilson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 38, 951; Prang, *Ann. Phys.*, 1938, 31, 681; Shrinivasan and Prasad, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 1462; Redlich and Bigeleisen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 758). The change is slight and Redlich and Bigeleisen by measuring density to an accuracy of 0.5 in a million have definitely established that the molar volume of an electrolyte is given by

$$v = V_0 + A\sqrt{C} + BC$$

where A and B are constant and A can be calculated on theoretical basis.

Not much work is done on apparent molar volume of non-electrolytes. Since high accuracy is required in determining density, it was considered advisable to measure the actual volume changes also. The known weight of the substance was added in a microburette and the known volume of water run in by another microburette. The volume change after the solid has dissolved was noted. The concentration of the solution was changed (a) by adding more and more of the solvent to the same solution, and (b) by taking different weights of the solid. Results are as follows. The whole work was carried out at constant room temperature of 20°.

TABLE I

Acetamide			Urea		
Wt. of substance.	Vol. increase (H ₂ O).	Wt. of one c.c.	Wt. of substance.	Vol. increase (H ₂ O).	Wt. of one c.c.
6.1220 g.	6.2 c.c.	1.008	6.1532	4.6	1.33
3.7530	3.4	1.1	4.8490	3.4	1.36
5.5928	5.4	1.03	2.0380	1.5	1.35
4.5900	4.35	1.05	3.0082	2.9	1.24

Dilution of the same solution from 20 c.c. to 50 c.c. did not show any further change in volume which could be detected (up to 0.05 c.c.).

We have for the mean molecular weight M of a solution.

$$M = (1-x)m_1 + xM_2$$

where m_1 is the molecular weight of solvent and M_2 , the molecular weight of solute. If d_1 and D are the densities of solvent and solution respectively, then $m_1/d_1 = v_1$, molecular volume of solvent and

$$M/D = \frac{m_1(1-x) + xM_2}{D}$$

But density D of the solution = $\frac{m_1(1-x) + xM_2}{(1-x)v_1 + xv_2}$

where v_2 is the volume of the solute in solution when molar weight is dissolved and that it does not change with dilution.

Hence

$$M/D = (1-x)v_1 + xv_2$$

or

$$\frac{M}{D} \cdot \frac{m_1}{d_1} = \frac{(1-x)v_1 + xv_2}{v_1}$$

Since $v_2/v_1 = m$ is constant as v_2 and v_1 are constant

$$\frac{M}{D} \cdot \frac{m_1}{d_1} = 1 + mx - x.$$

It is thus possible to determine m and hence see whether the volume change caused by dissolving a solid of known weight is constant and does not depend on dilution. The following table illustrates this.

TABLE II

Acetamide in water.					Urea in water.				
x .	M/D .	m_1/d_1 .	$\frac{M/D}{m_1/d_1}$.	m .	x .	M/D .	m_1/d_1 .	$\frac{M/D}{m_1/d_1}$.	m .
0.1792	24.16	18.03	1.339	2.89	0.0792	19.67	18.03	1.090	2.13
0.2290	26.03	18.03	1.443	2.94	0.0987	20.23	18.03	1.122	2.23
0.2818	27.90	18.03	1.547	2.94	0.1245	20.87	18.03	1.157	2.24
					0.1501	21.44	18.03	1.189	2.25
Cane sugar in water.					Glucose in water.				
0.0216	21.79	18.03	1.208	10.52	0.0154	19.35	18.03	1.073	5.73
0.0257	22.57	18.03	1.251	10.76	0.0236	19.67	18.03	1.102	5.34
0.0377	24.87	18.03	1.379	11.05	0.0320	20.64	18.03	1.144	5.50
					0.0369	21.07	18.03	1.168	5.55
					0.0613	23.21	18.03	1.286	5.66

For a ternary mixture containing X and Y molar fractions of solute whose molecular weights are m_2 and m_3

$$M = (1 - X - Y)m_1 + Xm_2 + Ym_3$$

$$d = \frac{(1 - X - Y)m_1 + Xm_2 + Ym_3}{(1 - X - Y)v_1 + Xv_2 + Yv_3}$$

where v_1 , v_2 and v_3 are the molar volumes in solution for the solvent and dissolved substances. Hence

$$M/d = (1 - X - Y)v_1 + Xv_2 + Yv_3 \quad (1)$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{M/d}{m_1/d_1} &= \frac{(1 - X - Y)v_1 + Xv_2 + Yv_3}{v_1} \\ &= (1 - X - Y) + mx + m'y \end{aligned}$$

where $m = v_2/v_1$ and $m' = v_3/v_1$ which are constant since molar volumes in solution are taken as constants.

TABLE III

Water, (X) Acetamide, (Y) Urea.

<i>M/d.</i>	$(1-X-Y)v_1 + X.v_2 + Y.v_3$
(i) $\frac{28.18}{1.07} = 26.33$	$0.7539 \times 18 + 0.164 \times 56.96 + 44.16 \times 0.0821 = 26.53$
(ii) $\frac{29.78}{1.095} = 27.19$	$0.7159 \times 18 + 0.1567 \times 56.96 + 44.16 \times 0.1274 = 27.43$
(iii) $\frac{31.87}{1.071} = 29.78$	$0.6636 \times 18 + 0.2627 \times 56.96 + 44.16 \times 0.0737 = 30.16$
(iv) $\frac{30.67}{1.078} = 28.45$	$0.6933 \times 18 + 0.2075 \times 56.96 + 0.0992 \times 44.16 = 28.688$

The molar volume of acetamide = 56.96 and of urea = 44.16 as determined before. The application of the formula is interesting, since it proves that even in ternary mixtures the volumes of these dissolved solids in solutions does not change to any marked extent.

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